

X-ray computed tomography-based modelling for feature-dependent and independent meshing of heterogeneous material

Robert M. Auenhammer^{1,2}, Lars P. Mikkelsen², Ragnar Larsson¹, Renaud Gutkin^{3,1}, Leif E. Asp¹

¹Industrial and Materials Science, Chalmers University of Technology, SE-412 96 Göteborg, Sweden

²Composites Manufacturing and Testing, Department of Wind and Energy Systems, Technical University of Denmark, DK-4000 Roskilde, Denmark

³Safety Centre, Volvo Car Corporation, SE-405 31 Göteborg, Sweden

Financed by:

The Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Network MUMMERING (Grant Agreement no. 765604)

Fordonsstrategiska Forskning och Innovation (Grant no. 2021-05062)

Imaged-based modelling

Imaged-based modelling

Accurate
modelling

Imaged-based modelling

Accurate
imaging

R. M. Auenhammer et al., Automated x-ray computer tomography segmentation method for finite element analysis of non-crimp fabric reinforced composites, *Composite Structures*, **256**, 113136 (2021)

M. Liebi et al., Nanostructure surveys of macroscopic specimens by small-angle scattering tensor tomography, *Nature* **527**, 349-352 (2015)

Imaged-based modelling

Imaged-based modelling

Accurate material behaviour prediction

X-ray computed tomography aided engineering (XAE) Process

CHALMERS

X-ray computed tomography aided engineering (XAE) Process

Image acquisition →

X-ray computed tomography aided engineering (XAE) Process

R. M. Auenhammer, L. P. Mikkelsen, L. E. Asp and B. J. Blinzler (2021) Automated x-ray computer tomography segmentation method for finite element analysis of non-crimp fabric reinforced composites, *Composite Structures*, **256**, 113136

Results

R. M. Auenhammer, N. Jeppesen, L. P. Mikkelsen, V. A. Dahl, L. E. Asp. X-ray computed tomography data structure tensor orientation mapping for finite element models — STXAE. Software Impacts 11 (2022), 100216

R. M. Auenhammer, N. Jeppesen, L. P. Mikkelsen, V. A. Dahl, B. J. Blinzler, L. E. Asp. Robust numerical analysis of fibrous composites from X-ray computed tomography image data enabling low resolutions, Composites Science and Technology, 256 (2022) 113136

Feature-dependent meshing

Feature-independent meshing

CHALMERS

Feature-independent meshing

CHALMERS

Feature-independent meshing

CHALMERS

Feature-independent meshing

Stress distribution

Stress histogram

Conclusion

- Image-based modelling adds complexity to the modelling process
- BUT allows for more accurate modelling

- Good match stress histogram

Acknowledgements

Thanks to my PhD supervisors

- L. Mikkelsen (DTU)
- R. Gutkin, R. Larsson and L. Asp (Chalmers)

Thanks to my co-authors

Thanks to the European Training Network MUMMERING for valuable collaboration and contributions to this work.

Thanks to the European Union for financial support via grant no. 765604.

Thanks to Fordonsstrategiska Forskning och Innovation for financial support via grant no. 2021-05062.

MUMMERING
H2020: 765604